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**ASSESSMENT OF MIGRATION, DISPLACEMENT AND RELIANCE ON
TRADITIONAL MEDICINE WITHIN INTERNALLY DISPLACE PERSONS CAMPS
IN NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERIA**

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Abstract: *This study examines the nexus between forced migration, displacement, and reliance on traditional medicine among Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in North-Central Nigeria, with emphasis on Benue, Nasarawa, and the Federal Capital Territory. Displacement in the region driven largely by farmer herder conflicts has pushed thousands into poorly resourced formal and informal camps where access to modern healthcare is severely constrained. Clinics are scarce, poorly staffed, and financially inaccessible, compelling many IDPs to depend on indigenous medical systems. Adopting a mixed-methods design, the research combines surveys (n = 500), in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions to capture both statistical trends and lived experiences of IDPs. Findings indicate that over 60% of displaced persons rely on herbal remedies, traditional birth attendants, and spiritual healers, far higher than rates among host communities. Key drivers of this reliance include affordability (68.4%), cultural familiarity (56.8%), accessibility (55.6%), and enduring trust in indigenous healing. Logistic regression further reveals significant associations between reliance on traditional medicine and socio-economic variables such as education level, income, and distance to healthcare facilities. The study concludes that displacement not only uproots populations but also reshapes healthcare-seeking strategies, making traditional medicine central to IDP survival. While culturally embedded and accessible, unregulated reliance on these practices raises concerns regarding safety and delayed treatment. The research recommends integrating traditional practitioners into humanitarian health systems, strengthening camp-based healthcare infrastructure, and developing regulatory frameworks to ensure safe and culturally responsive care.*

Keywords: Migration, Displacement, Traditional Medicine, IDPs, Healthcare Access, North-Central Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Internal displacement remains one of the most pressing humanitarian and developmental challenges globally. The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR, 2023) estimates that over 71.1 million people worldwide are currently internally displaced due to armed conflict, generalized violence,

natural disasters, and human rights violations. Africa, particularly the Lake Chad Basin, the Sahel, and the Horn of Africa, hosts a disproportionate share of these populations, with Nigeria ranked among the countries with the highest levels of displacement (IDMC, 2024).

Within Nigeria, recurrent farmer herder conflicts, communal clashes, banditry, and climate-related hazards have uprooted millions, forcing them into makeshift camps and urban host communities (Akinyemi & Isiugo-Abanihe, 2022). According to the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (2024), the North-Central region covering Benue, Nasarawa, Plateau, Niger, Kogi, and the Federal Capital Territory has experienced significant waves of forced migration. This region's cultural diversity, political marginalization, and ecological tensions make it a hotspot for protracted displacement (Okoli & Atelhe, 2021).

Displacement is not only a spatial disruption but also a determinant of health vulnerability. The collapse of livelihoods, overcrowded camps, and poor access to water and sanitation systems increase exposure to communicable diseases, while psychosocial trauma compounds the burden of ill health (Afolabi, Balogun, & Sunday, 2022; Sphere Association, 2018). Humanitarian responses in Nigeria have historically prioritized emergency relief, often overlooking sustainable healthcare delivery in IDP camps (Adamu, Usman, & Ibrahim, 2022). Clinics in many camps remain underfunded, understaffed, and inadequately supplied, leaving displaced populations with limited access to biomedical services.

Against this backdrop, traditional medicine emerges as both a coping strategy and a cultural resource. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) notes that in many African contexts, up to 80% of the population rely on indigenous systems of healing as their primary form of healthcare. For internally displaced persons, traditional healers, herbalists, spiritualists, and traditional birth attendants (TBAs) often provide the only accessible and affordable health services (Mande, 2020; Ibenegbu et al., 2021). This

reliance raises critical questions about health pluralism, cultural resilience, and the integration of traditional systems within humanitarian frameworks.

While the literature demonstrates the centrality of traditional medicine in African health systems, research specifically focusing on IDPs in North-Central Nigeria remains scarce. Most Nigerian studies concentrate on the North-East, given the prominence of Boko Haram-induced displacement (Yusuf et al., 2019; Ibenegbu et al., 2021). Limited scholarship has addressed how farmer herder conflicts and communal violence in the Middle Belt are reshaping healthcare-seeking behaviors.

Furthermore, few studies adopt a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative prevalence data with qualitative insights into cultural meanings and health perceptions. This gap underscores the relevance of the present study, which systematically examines how migration and displacement intersect with reliance on traditional medicine among IDPs in North-Central Nigeria.

While existing studies have examined health challenges among Nigerian IDPs, few have systematically explored the intersection of migration, displacement, and reliance on traditional medicine in North-Central Nigeria. This study therefore seeks to fill that gap by investigating the health-seeking strategies of IDPs and the role of traditional medicine in shaping resilience amidst systemic neglect.

STUDY AREA

North Central Nigeria, also known as the Middle Belt, is one of the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. It is a transitional region both ecologically and culturally, bridging the predominantly Muslim north and the largely Christian south. The zone comprises six states Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger,

Plateau and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Latitude: Between approximately 6°N and 11°N Longitude: Between 4°E and 10°E The region lies north of the southern rainforest and south of the Sahelian savanna, making it a central inland corridor in Nigeria. The region is characterized by a mix of plateaus, hills, valleys, and river basins. The Jos Plateau in Plateau State rises to over 1,200 meters above sea level, forming one of the highest points in Nigeria. River valleys such as those of the Benue and Niger Rivers dominate much of Kogi, Benue, and Niger States. North Central Nigeria experiences a tropical savanna climate (Aw) with distinct wet and dry seasons. Rainfall averages between 1,000 mm and

1,600 mm annually, while mean annual temperatures range from 24°C to 32°C. The region falls mainly within the Guinea Savannah zone, characterized by grasses interspersed with shrubs and scattered trees. Rich soils make the region suitable for agriculture, especially yam, maize, and rice cultivation. Major rivers include:

- River Niger (flows through Niger and Kogi States)
- River Benue (flows through Benue and Kogi States)

These rivers and their tributaries support irrigation, fishing, and domestic water use. The region is endowed with abundant solid minerals: tin (Plateau), limestone (Kogi), gold (Niger), and coal (Benue). Fertile soils and forests also contribute significantly to agricultural productivity.

Figure 1: North-Central Nigeria Showing Internally Displaced Persons Camps.
Source: Adapted from Kogi State Ministry of Land and Survey.

The region is ethnically diverse, home to many minority ethnic groups such as the Tiv, Nupe, Gbagyi, Idoma, Igala, Berom, Ebir, and others. It includes Abuja, Nigeria's capital, making it politically and administratively significant. Urban centers include Makurdi, Lokoja, Minna, Jos, Ilorin, and Lafia, as well as many rural communities. North Central Nigeria serves as a transportation corridor linking northern and southern Nigeria. It plays a key role in national integration, agriculture, and internal migration. The region has also experienced conflicts, including farmer-herder clashes and displacement, contributing to the growth of IDP camps.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative component involved the use of structured questionnaire to gather measurable data on the prevalence and patterns of traditional medicine use among IDPs. The qualitative component includes in-depth interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs) to explore cultural beliefs, personal experiences, and perceptions regarding traditional health practices in displacement contexts. This design allows for triangulation and enriches the interpretation of findings.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted: Purposive sampling was used to select three states (Benue, Nasarawa, and FCT) due to their high concentration of IDPs. In each state, two IDP camps (one formal and one informal) were selected based on population size and accessibility. Within each camp, systematic random sampling was used to select

households, and stratified sampling was used to ensure representation across sex and age groups. A total of 500 respondents participated in the quantitative survey (approximately 80–90 per camp), while 20 key informants and 6 FGDs (2 per state) were conducted for the qualitative component.

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

The following instruments and methods were used: Questionnaire A structured questionnaire was designed to collect information on: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics, Experiences of displacement, Health challenges, Use and perception of traditional medicine, Accessibility and affordability of healthcare services. The questionnaire consisted mainly of closed-ended questions and was administered with the assistance of trained field enumerators.

METHODS OF DATA ANALYSIS

Quantitative data collected through questionnaires were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean scores) were used to summarize data. Inferential statistics such as chi-square tests and binary logistic regression were used to assess relationships between socio-economic variables and reliance on traditional medicine.

Transcripts from interviews and FGDs were analyzed using thematic content analysis. Responses were grouped under themes such as health-seeking behavior, cultural beliefs, barriers to healthcare access, and perceptions of traditional medicine. Manual coding and NVivo software were used to manage and interpret the data.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical approval was obtained from a recognized institutional review board. Key ethical procedures included: Informed consent from all participants, Confidentiality and anonymity of responses, Voluntary participation with the option to withdraw at any point, Data protection and secure storage of records, Special care was taken when working with vulnerable populations, such as elderly IDPs and women, to ensure sensitivity and cultural appropriateness.

LIMITATIONS OF THE METHODOLOGY

While every effort was made to ensure the robustness of the methodology, some limitations are acknowledged: Accessibility issues in some informal camps due to poor roads or security concerns, Language barriers which required translation in some areas, potentially affecting the interpretation of certain responses, Emotional distress or trauma in some respondents which may have influenced recall accuracy, Nonetheless, these limitations were mitigated through adequate planning, use of local research assistants, and ethical safeguards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents and analyzes the data collected through structured questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions (FGDs) across selected Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) camps in Benue,

Nasarawa, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The analysis addresses the study's objectives, focusing on the drivers of displacement, challenges in accessing healthcare, the prevalence of traditional medicine use, and the socio-cultural factors influencing reliance on traditional healthcare among IDPs.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Table 1: Presents result on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The results show that out of the 500 respondents, females constituted 59.2%, while males accounted for 40.8%. The dominance of women reflects the demographic vulnerability of displacement, where men are often victims of conflict-related fatalities or remain behind to protect land and property. Similar sex imbalances were reported by Adamu, Usman, & Ibrahim (2022), who found that women and children constitute the majority of IDPs in Nasarawa State.

In terms of age, the largest proportion of respondents fell within the 31–50 years age group (45.6%), followed by those aged 18–30 years (26.4%) and 51 years and above (28.0%). This distribution suggests that displacement disproportionately affects individuals within their most productive years, thereby disrupting livelihoods and community stability. The high proportion of widowed and divorced respondents (13.6%) also underscores the disintegration of family structures due to violent conflicts.

Table1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	204	40.8%
	Female	296	59.2%
Total		500	100%
Age Group	18–30	132	26.4%
	31–50	228	45.6%
	51 and above	140	28.0%
Total		500	100%
Marital Status	Single	118	23.6%
	Married	314	62.8%
	Widowed/Divorced	68	13.6%
Total		500	100%
Education Level	No formal education	142	28.4%
	Primary	160	32.0%
	Secondary	138	27.6%
	Tertiary	60	12.0%
Total		500	100%
Occupation	Farming	210	42.0%
	Petty Trading	102	20.4%
	Artisan/Manual work	98	19.6%
	Unemployed	90	18.0%
Total		500	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Educational attainment was generally low, with 28.4% of respondents having no formal education, 32.0% with only primary education, and only 12.0% attaining tertiary education. This weak educational profile has direct implications for healthcare choices, as those with lower education are statistically more likely to rely on traditional medicine. Yusuf, Mohammed, & Adamu (2019) similarly observed that low literacy levels among displaced populations in North-East Nigeria limited their ability to navigate formal healthcare systems.

The occupational background prior to displacement reveals that 42.0% were farmers, 20.4% petty traders, and 19.6% artisans/manual workers. This confirms that

agrarian communities are disproportionately affected by farmer–herder conflicts, leading to large-scale disruption of rural livelihoods and reinforcing reliance on low-cost traditional healthcare practices.

CAUSES OF DISPLACEMENT

Table 2: Presents information on causes of displacement. The analysis shows that the farmer–herder conflict accounted for 58.8% of displacements, followed by communal violence (25.2%), banditry/insecurity (9.6%), and natural disasters (6.4%). These findings highlight the dominance of anthropogenic drivers over natural hazards in shaping displacement patterns in the Middle Belt.

Table 2: Causes of Displacement

Cause of Displacement	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Farmer–Herder Conflict	294	58.8%
Communal Violence	126	25.2%
Natural Disaster (flood, drought)	32	6.4%
Banditry/Insecurity	48	9.6%
Total	500	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The farmer herder crisis, particularly acute in Benue and Nasarawa, reflects long-standing disputes over land, grazing routes, and water resources. Okoli & Atelhe (2021) similarly emphasize that resource-based clashes are the principal cause of displacement in Benue State. The relatively lower percentage of displacements attributed to natural disasters suggests that structural violence, rather than climate variability, remains the major determinant of forced migration in this region.

ACCESS TO MODERN HEALTHCARE IN IDP CAMPS

Table 3: Presents data on Access to modern healthcare in IDP camps. The results reveal glaring inadequacies in healthcare access: only 31.2% reported the presence of a health facility within the camp, and just 23.6% had access to trained health workers. Similarly, 79.2% lacked access to affordable drugs, while 73.2% reported that the nearest hospital was more than three kilometers away.

Table 3: Access to Modern Healthcare in IDP Camps

Access to Modern Healthcare in the Camps	Response	Response
Healthcare Indicator	Yes	No
Health facility within the camp	156 (31.2%)	344 (68.8%)
Presence of trained health workers	118 (23.6%)	382 (76.4%)
Access to affordable drugs	104 (20.8%)	396 (79.2%)
Distance to nearest hospital (>3km)	366 (73.2%)	134 (26.8%)
Total	500(100%)	500(100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

This paints a grim picture of systemic neglect in humanitarian healthcare delivery. According to Afolabi, Balogun, & Sunday (2022), healthcare in IDP camps across Plateau State is similarly characterized by underfunding, poor staffing, and erratic drug supplies. The absence of adequate healthcare facilities forces IDPs to explore culturally familiar alternatives such as traditional medicine, highlighting the

functional void filled by indigenous health systems.

Trust Deficit in Formal Healthcare: Participants cited negligence, long waiting times, and lack of drugs in formal clinics.

“Even when we go to the health post, they send us back because there’s no medicine or doctor.” (Elderly woman, FCT camp).

PREVALENCE OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE USE

Table 4: Presents information on the prevalence of traditional medicine use. The findings demonstrate that reliance on

traditional medicine is widespread. Herbal medicine was used by 62.4% of respondents, followed by traditional birth attendants (45.6%), spiritual/faith healing (41.2%), and bone setting (14.8%). Furthermore, 35.6% reported combining both traditional and modern medicine, a pattern of pluralistic healthcare-seeking behavior.

Table 4: Prevalence of Traditional Medicine Use

Traditional Practice Used	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Herbal medicine	312	62.4%
Traditional birth attendants (TBAs)	228	45.6%
Spiritual/faith healing	206	41.2%
Bone setting	74	14.8%
Combination of traditional and modern medicine	178	35.6%
Total	500	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

This supports the assertion by the World Health Organization (2021) that displaced populations often adopt medical pluralism to cope with inadequate formal healthcare. The high use of TBAs reflects the urgent maternal health needs of displaced women, who often lack access to skilled birth attendants. Mande (2020) also found that TBAs remain crucial for maternal care among displaced women in Nasarawa State, especially where formal maternity clinics are absent. Herbal medicine and TBAs are the most used forms of traditional healthcare. Many respondents also reported using both traditional and modern systems concurrently, indicating pluralistic health-seeking behavior.

Several themes emerged from interviews with IDPs and traditional practitioners:

Cultural Continuity: Many IDPs emphasized the emotional and cultural comfort derived

from traditional healing. *“We trust the herbs from our fathers more than hospitals that demand money we don’t have.”* (Male IDP, Benue).

Gendered Health Practices: Women noted the importance of TBAs, especially in the absence of maternity clinics.

“I delivered both children here with a woman who helps us. The hospital is too far.” (Female IDP, Nasarawa).

DRIVERS OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE USE

Table 5: Presents results on drivers of traditional medicine use. The reasons for using traditional medicine include affordability (68.4%), cultural familiarity (56.8%),

accessibility (55.6%), trust in effectiveness (39.2%), and religious beliefs (20.4%). This

shows that economic factors dominate but are reinforced by cultural and spiritual considerations.

Table 5: Drivers of Traditional Medicine Use

Reason	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Affordability	342	68.4%
Cultural familiarity	284	56.8%
Accessibility	278	55.6%
Trust in effectiveness	196	39.2%
Religious beliefs	102	20.4%
Total	500	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Affordability is particularly important in a context where displacement erodes livelihoods, rendering orthodox healthcare financially inaccessible. Cultural familiarity and religious influences further reinforce the appeal of traditional medicine. These findings align with Afolabi et al. (2022), who emphasized that displaced persons in Plateau State preferred indigenous healers due to affordability and deep-rooted cultural trust.

Mixed-Use Patterns: Many reported combining both systems.

“We go to hospital if it’s serious, but herbs work for fever and pain.” (Youth FGD, Benue).

Using chi-square tests and binary logistic regression:

Education level was significantly associated with traditional medicine use ($p < 0.05$); those with lower education were more likely to rely on traditional methods.

Income level and distance to nearest hospital also showed significant correlations with higher traditional medicine use.

sex was not statistically significant, though women reported higher use of TBAs in qualitative discussions.

Chi-square and logistic regression analyses revealed significant associations between traditional medicine use and socioeconomic variables such as education, income, and distance to healthcare facilities. Respondents with lower education and income were more likely to depend on traditional medicine, while distance (>3 km) to healthcare facilities also increased reliance on indigenous remedies.

Interestingly, sex was not statistically significant, though qualitative discussions suggested that women made greater use of TBAs. This discrepancy highlights the limitations of purely quantitative measures and the value of integrating qualitative evidence.

These findings align with WHO (2021), which notes that socioeconomic deprivation and spatial exclusion are global determinants of traditional medicine reliance, particularly in displacement contexts.

The study underscores that displacement not only dislocates populations geographically but also reshapes healthcare behavior. Traditional medicine emerges as both a coping strategy and a reaffirmation of cultural identity in the face of systemic neglect. While traditional medicine offers affordability and accessibility, its unregulated use poses risks such as delayed treatment, unsafe practices, and dependence on unverified remedies.

However, dismissing these practices would be counterproductive. Instead, the findings suggest the need for integrative healthcare approaches that recognize, regulate, and collaborate with traditional healers within IDP camps. Such models, as advocated by WHO (2021), can ensure safer, culturally sensitive, and more sustainable healthcare for displaced populations.

Displacement is primarily driven by conflict, especially farmer–herder clashes.

IDPs face major healthcare barriers limited infrastructure, cost, distance, and poor staffing.

Over 60% of IDPs depend on traditional medicine, especially herbal remedies and traditional birth attendants.

Use of traditional medicine is driven by affordability, accessibility, cultural familiarity, and perceived effectiveness.

Socioeconomic status and education level significantly influence health-seeking choices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that displacement in North-Central Nigeria is primarily conflict-induced and has severely disrupted both livelihoods and healthcare access. In the absence of reliable formal healthcare, IDPs

have increasingly turned to traditional medicine, not merely as an alternative but as a central survival strategy.

Traditional medicine, particularly herbal remedies and TBAs, provides affordability, accessibility, and cultural resonance. However, its unregulated use carries potential health risks, including misdiagnosis, unsafe delivery practices, and delayed access to orthodox treatment. The persistence of traditional healing among IDPs therefore reflects both resilience and vulnerability.

Crucially, the study challenges the dominant narrative in humanitarian health interventions, which often marginalizes traditional medicine. It argues that indigenous health systems must be recognized and strategically integrated into displacement healthcare frameworks. Failure to do so risks ignoring the lived realities of millions of displaced persons who rely on these systems daily.

Thus, the findings underscore the need for inclusive, integrative, and culturally sensitive health models that combine the strengths of both orthodox and traditional practices in displacement contexts.

In doing so, humanitarian and government agencies must move beyond emergency relief toward sustainable, culturally sensitive health systems that reflect the realities of displacement. By engaging traditional practitioners as partners rather than competitors, health responses can become both safer and more effective.

This contribution not only fills a research gap in the Nigerian Middle Belt but also offers broader lessons for displacement contexts across sub-Saharan Africa and beyond. It highlights the importance of recognizing indigenous health systems within global humanitarian discourse, reaffirming that

resilience in displacement is as much cultural as it is structural.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

(i) Integration of Traditional Practitioners into Primary Healthcare Systems; government health agencies and humanitarian organizations should formally recognize, register, and collaborate with traditional medicine practitioners operating in IDP camps. Training should be provided on hygiene, safe delivery, and referral systems to ensure patient safety and reduce risks of complications. Traditional healers could serve as first-contact providers, especially in maternal and child healthcare, under supervised frameworks.

(ii) Strengthening Healthcare Infrastructure in IDP Camps; government should establish fully equipped and functional primary healthcare centers in both formal and informal IDP camps. Ensure consistent provision of essential drugs, laboratory services, and skilled health personnel, including midwives

and doctors. Deploy mobile clinics to reach camps in remote or insecure locations.

(iii) Health Education and Sensitization Campaigns; there is the need to implement culturally sensitive health education programs to inform IDPs about safe health practices, risks of unsafe remedies, and the importance of timely referrals to hospitals. Special campaigns should target women and caregivers, promoting supervised antenatal and postnatal care.

(iv) Policy Development and Regulation; national and state governments should develop policies that promote collaboration between orthodox and traditional medicine systems in humanitarian contexts. Quality control, licensing, and monitoring mechanisms should be enforced for traditional practitioners to ensure safety and standardization of practices.

(v) Research and Monitoring; further research should be encouraged to explore variations in traditional medicine use across different ethnic groups, age cohorts, and displacement settings. Longitudinal monitoring of health outcomes among IDPs using traditional medicine is essential to inform policy decisions and humanitarian planning.

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